

Recommended citation: Yustyk, I. V., & Lutsenko, G. V. (2020).
Implementation of Digital Literacy Course in the First-Year Engineering
Students' Curriculum. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen,
H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI
48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1204-1214). European Society for Engineering
Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654227.

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL LITERACY COURSE IN THE FIRST-YEAR ENGINEERING STUDENTS' CURRICULUM

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Conference Key Areas: *Future engineering skills, E-learning, blended learning, virtual reality*

Keywords: *digital literacy, blended learning setting, BYOD*

ABSTRACT

Digital Literacy has become a key skill for 21st century engineers that corresponds to the demands of Industry 4.0. On the other hand, the Digital Literacy level has an impact on learning process at university, including engineering curriculum, learning practices etc. In our work, we describe an example of integration Digital Literacy course "Information and Communication Technologies" in the curriculum of first-year engineering students. This course was designed by using blended learning strategies as well as BYOD (bring your own device) technology. We emphasize that the inclusion of such course in the curriculum fosters the development of digital literacy skills of first-year students and create the preconditions for the formation of an effective personal learning environment. The research question was to evaluate the level of digital literacy of freshman students and analyze the Digital Literacy Course impact on students' preparedness to use the ICT during the learning process. Such course was implemented for the students of different specialties. It gave a possibility to analyze the differences between engineering students and representatives of other specialties. The survey was carried out which includes the question related to tools, which students use during the lessons. The purposes of different tools using including teamwork and problem solving have been analyzed. As a result, the improvement of Digital Literacy skills of first-year engineering students was observed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Development of Industry 4.0 has a profound effect on modern engineering. Digital transformation is accompanied by the accelerated introduction of modern technologies and creates conditions for changing business models and accelerating innovative development. The driving factors behind the transformation of jobs are the widespread adoption of high-speed mobile Internet, the development of artificial intelligence and its applications, and the widespread use of big data and cloud technologies. The introduction of innovative technologies into the practice of engineering is intensifying, including Big Data Analysis, Internet of Things, Machine Learning, Virtual Reality, etc. New job trends include the increasing flexibility of the labour market, the decentralization of work operations and the increasing share of remote workers [1].

The above factors determine the relevance of the development of digital competence of engineering students since the first years of study. The CDIO Standards 3.0 proposal states, "Digitalization can be argued to be a major enabler for reforming both engineering work and ways of learning how to engineer." [2, p. 3]. Thus, the current level of digital competence for first-year students is an essential prerequisite for their successful inclusion in the educational process at the university and the formation of personal learning environment (PLE). The educational process in higher education is focused on a higher level of autonomy and responsibility, an active role of the student in building their educational trajectory, intensive interaction of students in groups in the course of completing tasks of both online and offline communication. In our opinion, timely and sufficient assessment of the current level of digital competence of first-year students will help solve the problem of adaptation.

Also, one of the challenges for higher education is to encourage students to use the learning approaches that lead to the highest quality learning outcomes and develop flexible competencies. In this paper, we are talking about research conducted during the academic semester and aimed at improving the quality of education of students of various specialities in the implementation of digital technologies and services for the course "Information and Communication Technologies" (ICT). Although the study of certain aspects of students' digital competence required for further professional and educational development was conducted within one course only, a wide range of subjects for which discipline was read and different types of samples led to statistically significant improvements in the quality of students' learning approaches.

In this paper, we present the on-going experience and preliminary findings concerning (i) the design and implementation of integration Digital Literacy course "Information and Communication Technologies" in the curriculum of first-year engineering students, (ii) the investigation of the influence of this course on the development of digital skills of first-year engineering students as well as their preparedness to the formation of own PLE. Due to the fact that a similar course was also introduced for students of natural sciences and humanities, we were able to compare the results and highlight those areas that need further improvement specifically for engineering students.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The use of Digital Literacy concept has been widespread since 1997 when Gilster defined Digital Literacy as 'literacy for a digital age' [3]. Since then, the both terms

Digital Competence and Digital Literacy have been increasingly referred to as official documentation of government agencies and international organizations, and indeed in scientific researches [4].

In 2006, the European Commission recognized Digital Competence as one of eight key competencies for lifelong learning. It emphasized the critical connection of Digital Competence with such areas of human life as employment, training, leisure and socialization. For the time being, the EC Digital Competence is following: "digital competence involves the confident, critical and responsible use of, and engagement with, digital technologies for learning, at work, and for participation in society". The Digital Competence framework consists of 21 competencies divided into the following five areas: information and data literacy; communication and collaboration; digital content creation (including programming); safety (including digital well-being and competencies related to cybersecurity) and problem-solving [5].

It should be noted that the structure of Digital Literacy/Digital Competence and approaches to describing it, presented in research publications, vary, which allows us to interpret the term as an umbrella term. Thus, when defining Digital Literacy, researchers refer to the ideas of cognitive skills and competencies, the importance of critical thinking and high-level thinking skills, and not only to the level of development of technical skills in computer technology [4, 6].

In the educational process, Digital Literacy is interpreted as an important prerequisite that determines students' readiness to successfully learn in the context of online and offline learning integrations, be flexible and adapt to change (which has proven relevant in recent months as students in most countries have gone online to study). Learning about and with digital technologies is defined as one of twelve different areas of Digital Competence [7]. As experience shows, among the educational practices having a positive impact on the development of advanced Digital Competence, researchers and practitioners highlight evidence-based practice, problem-based learning, case-based learning, project-based and design-based learning. Also, Graham defines four key characteristics of engineering programmes: a combination of digital and student activating learning forms, educational arrangements with a high degree of flexibility and diversity, global and multidisciplinary elements, as well as design projects that at the same time offer opportunities for reflection on technology development and own learning [2, 8].

The combination of active learning and digitization is provided within the blended learning framework that was used in our course. It is worth noting that the impetus for the study was due to two reasons. First, teachers are dissatisfied with the level of digital competence in the distance and blended learning. Second, an analysis of students' perceptions of modern information technology to work as a team, to solve problematic tasks and to study showed that 96% of students use smartphones [9] for training and personal use. Looking at Learning Management Systems (LMS) statistics in the United States, over 60% of students use LMS effectively in each discipline learning.

The situation in Ukraine is far from the same. As practice shows, first-year students who come to study from major cities have some experience with a variety of training systems and cloud services. Still, most have only a distant understanding of working online, of teamwork in electronic applications to solve problematic tasks effectively.

Moreover, first-year students do not understand the basic principles of Digital Literacy for learning.

We invest in the concept of Digital Literacy a little more than an individual's ability to evaluate and systematize information using information technology [10]. Digital Literacy ranks second among important 21st-century skills that modern professionals need to possess. The ability to use advanced digital technologies effectively and safely in work and study is Digital Literacy. That is, this can also include the understanding of secure online interaction, the ability to extract information that is irrelevant or that may contain plagiarism. In this case, the specialist must also produce reliable data, be able to simplify and interpret the information in a convenient way for the user. And for this, he must use services and technologies that are close to the average citizen (infographics, videographics, animated 3D drawings, which easily display information on mobile devices) [11]. It can be concluded that Digital Literacy is based on the concepts of visual, computer and information literacy [12].

3 COURSE DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

The prerequisites for the importance of Digital Literacy have been used as the basis for a study conducted for the ICT course. Such course was included in almost all degree programmes at [name of university] since the 2019–2020 academic year. For various specialities, it is offered in the first or second semester. This course has a total of 3 credits from the ECTS, which is equivalent to 90 hours. The study was conducted for 130 students, among them, 60 students are of humanities, and 70 students are of engineering and applied physics specialities.

Our research is work-in-progress. Therefore, the choice of the case study method was based on the fact that the ICT course was introduced for the first time, so our activity was primarily aimed at accumulating empirical data. It is assumed that these data will help to answer the research questions, and will determine the further university strategy for creating the conditions to form a digital competence (Fig. 1) in students.

According to the scheme, the topics students studied during the semester included: creating a personal e-learning environment (review of LMS, Google applications for data management automation and storage), organization and teamwork support (the concept analysis of the project and its components, time management, collaboration and services that provide project management and further communication between team members), the concept of digital literacy and Internet safety (rules review of online interaction, services of testing their own digital literacy after writing Ukrainian and English texts), the concept of academic integrity (data analysis and services review for plagiarism), data search, analysis and systematization (scientometric databases, managing of scientific texts, creating a scientific profile and searching for information by keywords and other means in the network), work with the content management services (creating documents with different data formats, working with online Google spreadsheets, creating presentations and knowledge maps in various cloud services), applications for the research and projects presentation (review of preparation tools, rules for successful presentation, apps for creating info- and videographics, videos). All topics focused on tools, cloud services and programs that will help students learn the information and communication technologies essential to support their educational process at the university and after its completion. Due to this

selection of topics, we were able to significantly increase the level of digital literacy among students after the course.

All practical tasks provided by the course were divided into two categories: mastering the technical skills of owning services and Internet applications and tasks for the high-level thinking skills development: creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Practical tasks that develop critical thinking, students' creativity and the ability to solve problems were mostly performed during classroom work. There were a few common practices we used in our classes: the "World Cafe" method for the problem analysis and ways to solve it, the "Why?" method for structuring the problem-solving aspects, the marshmallow challenge for testing inclusion in teamwork, the "Disney's Three Chairs" task, which develops creativity while finding solutions to a problem. The online part included technical tasks, which involved the skills of online services and programs acquirement. Before this, theoretical aspects and issues of the application functionality were covered in the classroom.

The level of tasks complexity was determined by how many applications had to be considered when studying one topic, the number varied from 3 to 5 tasks. Besides, the issues were formed in accordance with Bloom's taxonomy, which provided for a gradual increase in the level of individual aspects complexity of each task. For students who studied in non-technical specialities, from time to time, it was challenging to perform some tasks on time, due to lack of knowledge of working with standard services and Internet applications.

All methods ensured the fulfilment of the research goal, which was to improve students' digital competence in the ICT subject, using aspects of approaches to blended learning and project activities. In the case of our study, qualitative and quantitative data were used.

The discipline formation plan was developed based on Table 1. Thus, the sources of information are the feedback of teachers who conducted classes with students about the peculiarities of the organization of the educational process and student surveys. In order to design the survey, theoretical material on the structure and content of digital competence was elaborated, as well as a number of questionnaires used by educational institutions and individual researchers. The table provides a framework of factors around which to develop the learning environment and assessment activities of the students. Factors have also been suggested logically, which may increase students' chances of perceiving the subject environment as an encouraging and supportive approach to problem-based learning.

From this, it becomes clear that the student must have the skills to use digital services at the technical and communication level. That is why it was important to form a discipline based on the needs of computer technology when a student is working on blended learning technology and is engaged in solving various team tasks.

Fig. 1. Characteristics of Digital Literacy

Table 1. Factors more likely to improve digital literacy in ICT discipline

The digital-based learning environment. The following factors are essential to achieving a learning context likely to encourage digital competencies approaches:

1. *The discipline has a clear structure.*
2. *A convenient LMS is used to present the materials.*
3. *Organization of discipline by BYOD technology (i.e. it is convenient to study using any device).*
4. *Tasks are created according to Bloom's taxonomy and meet the goals and requirements for blended learning.*
5. *Students receive a more personalized education.*
6. *Part of the tasks inclines to group work on the joint project.*
7. *Course objectives provide for the formation of a personal digital environment.*
8. *The teaching is flexible and provided with constant teacher support.*
9. *The problematic tasks to the topics stimulate the development of critical thinking.*
10. *Maintaining constant feedback after each lesson completion.*

Learning activities should:

1. *Be creative and experiential.*
2. *Encourage the study of cloud services and technologies.*
3. *Improve the quality of Google Docs usage.*
4. *Ensure effective retrieval, selection and presentation of information from the network.*
5. *Tackle real-world problems that will echo with the students' experiences.*
6. *Ensure effective presentation of research findings.*
7. *Ensure the effective use of social networks for work and study.*

In addition, the modern development of information technology has led to the creation of a course based on services and technologies already owned by students and which they can directly use during their studies [13]. Therefore, it was one of the reasons to use BYOD (Bring Your Own Device) technology as technical support of ICT discipline. Having conducted the survey, students in almost the vast majority (98 %) decided that they would work on smartphones.

4 FINDINGS

After the preliminary survey, at the beginning of the semester, students were informed that this subject would be taught and organized differently from other disciplines at the university. We shared the goals of the ICT discipline, the BYOD approach, the concept of blended learning, digital competence. The students realized that the changes had been made for a specific purpose, and met modern requirements for the future specialist. Discussing changes with students was an important first step in engaging them in the course design process, and it was a key criterion for further effective research.

The course was divided into eight topics, with one specific topic for every two weeks. During the semester, students started a joint project, which they defended at the end of the course. The purpose of the team project was to conduct a study of a product (sociological survey, creation of a device, stand, software application, video, etc.) for their professional activities and to explain its advantages and disadvantages over the products of this category.

Theoretical training was carried out in advance, and in the classes, the students performed problematic tasks, discussed unclear moments and intensive practical activities on studying the means of information technology. All topics prompted more attention to the technical components of the services and devices on which they

worked, the development of critical thinking, time management and presentation of the results of the tasks. The contact hours of the student teachers were transferred to the online network, which increased the support of learning twice and eliminated the barrier between the teacher and the student, prompted more questions from the student. Students received specific assignments and theoretical materials for each topic in LMS Google Apps for Education. Reflection was provided by an entry and exit ticket (expectations and "exit ticket"), which made it possible to shape the expectations of each topic better and improve the tasks of the following issues after the feedback. Approaches to student learning in 2019 were evaluated to inform the stages of reflection and work out of the research cycle of action. Overall, the activity of 12 groups was analysed before and after the course (Table 2). The data were collected using an anonymous questionnaire on Google Forms.

Table 2. Elements of the short-answer questionnaire used at the beginning of the study

1.	How long have you been using a personal computer (PC)?
2.	What types of devices do you use?
3.	For what purpose do you use a desktop computer or laptop?
4.	What types of mobile device do you use?
5.	For what purpose do you use mobile devices?
6.	Do you know how to work with LMS?
7.	How did you find out about new digital technologies?
8.	How would you rate your typing skills?
9.	How would you rate your web search skills?
10.	How would you rate your computer literacy skills (ability to use a computer)?

Survey results show that students mainly use laptops and smartphones for social networking, gaming and personal communication. Although the age of students varied from 16 to 18 years, and the use of digital technology was around 8-10 years, this did not affect the deeper purpose of technology for teaching and further professional activity.

The assessment of the subject consisted of a baseline questionnaire (see Table 3) in which students determined the level of ownership of different technologies and competences after completing the course. This task was designed to require students to reflect on their learning and therefore, to encourage a more technical approach to learning.

Table 3. Questionnaire elements used to investigate changes in the use of digital technologies

1.	Can you create and update web pages?
2.	Can you record and edit digital videos?
3.	Do you feel competent in using digital learning resources?
4.	Do you use social networking services?
5.	Is it easy for you to learn something by reading it on your computer screen?
6.	Do you have any mobile apps that you use to learn languages?
7.	Do you use Google Docs services?
8.	Please indicate your frequency of use for each of the following means by placing the pointer in the appropriate box: "Very often", "Frequently", "Sometimes", "Rarely", or "Never".
9.	What do you think are the factors that influence the use of digital technology?

All tasks involved assessing students' level of competence. The digital proficiency level results (see Table 4) showed a statistically significant change in the educational approaches used by students before and after the course.

Table 4. Analysis of digital literacy levels before and after completing the ICT course

Digital literacy tools	Before taking the course				After passing the course			
	Engineering		Humanities		Engineering		Humanities	
	Number of students (General 60)	%						
Usage of mobile applications for training	29	41	20	38	60	86	46	77
Usage LMS	23	33	16	27	61	87	55	92
Usage of cloud services for training	39	56	27	45	55	79	39	65
Search for information on the network	58	83	41	68	63	90	51	85
Presentation of digital business results (presentations, infographics, video content)	37	53	34	57	62	89	48	80

5 DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to increase the proportion of students who have ICT using digital literacy techniques. It was partially achieved after the end of the experiment. More than 56 % (n = 72) of students were classified as using several digital literacy increase techniques.

Overall, there is a significant increase in digital literacy among first-year students. It can be concluded that the implementation of the ICT course focuses on digital competence, which are:

1. Motivates students to learn through the constant inclusion and ease of use of different technological environments.
2. It covers students of different learning and thinking styles.
3. Allows students to create their unique products that reflect their personality and learning needs.
4. Provides more efficient search, selection and management of media to build your content.
5. Allows students to more creatively and efficiently share their achievements with the environment.
6. Will enable students to explore technological environments, which inevitably enhances the job skills that employers seek in today's professionals.

On the other hand, studies have shown that further increasing the proportion of students who will effectively use digital literacy tools in higher education is not an easy task. Achieving a significant effect takes time and some changes to the learning environment.

Although the proportion of students who have improved their digital literacy levels has increased since the beginning of the semester, some issues should be addressed.

An essential aspect of the study was the qualitative comparison of digital skills and the speed of mastering new information competencies between engineering students and

humanities students. The study found that engineering students were better able to learn certain services and technologies that they did not possess before studying the discipline. Critical thinking and constructiveness, consistency of problem-solving among these students were more noticeable in the course of practical work.

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Students' perceptions of overload were an important factor in the relative underperformance of the experiment. Most of the respondents in the survey noted that there were many tasks and sometimes the technical complexity of some of them reduced the level of motivation to study.

More than 55 % of students indicated problems with time to complete tasks. The problem with the perception of time to teach ICT may well be the load on other subjects that students have studied. Engineering students typically have about six to eight courses per semester (18 weeks), with up to three assignments per topic. By gradually reducing the load on the subject, you will be able to solve the problem.

6 CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research conducted here indicates that the prospect of further teaching ICT based on digital literacy can be an impulse to erase the boundaries between different disciplines and specialities. First, only high-quality, in-depth approaches to learning can lead to high-quality higher education outcomes. Second, large-scale interventions may be resource-intensive and may not always be optimal for the student.

The results of the study showed a statistically significant improvement in the proportion of students who have improved their digital skills, and indicate the need to continue implementing the ICT course in all areas of undergraduate training. A broader context involves changing the meaning of teaching other subjects and studying at the university. Impacting different components of the broader context is likely to be challenging. Changes in the level of the course and the context of study will need to influence the teachers of other subjects of the course.

The variability in the study of the percentage of students using digital competency tools (see Table 4) emphasizes the need for continued action research. Research is needed to confirm that the 2019 results were not one-offs but a consequence of changing learning approaches. Additional research is also planned, which will include in-depth interviews that explore students' perceptions of their use of ICT skills in their further professional and educational activities. Only by acquiring such knowledge, we will be able to hope for improvement of learning environments and the better development of students in society.

7 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work was carried out with the support of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (state registration number 0117U003909).

REFERENCES

- [1] World Economic Forum, "The Future of Jobs Report 2018," World Economic Forum, Geneva, Switzerland, 2018.
- [2] J. Malmqvist, M. K. Wedel, U. Lundqvist, K. Edstrom, A. Rosén, T. F. Astrup, M. Vigild, P. Munkebo Hussman, A. Grom, R. Lyng, S. Gunnarsson, H. Leong and A. Kamp, "Towards CDIO Standards 3.0," in *Proceedings of the 15th International CDIO Conference*, Aarhus, Denmark, 2019.
- [3] P. Hagel, "Towards an understanding of 'Digital Literacy(ies)'," Deakin University Library research & practice, Geelong, 2015.
- [4] M. Spante, S. S. Hashemi, M. Lundin and A. Algeres, "Digital competence and digital literacy in higher education research: Systematic review of concept use," *Cogent Education*, vol. 5, pp. 1-21, 2018.
- [5] EC, "European Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp)," 2020. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/escopedia/European_Digital_Competence_Framework_for_Citizens__40_DigComp_41_.
- [6] J.-M. Gulliot, S. Garlatti and G. Simon, "Impact of Digital Literacy on Graduate Engineer Curriculum," in *Proceedings of the 6th International CDIO Conference*, École Polytechnique, Montréal, June 15-18, 2010, 2010.
- [7] J. Janssen, S. Stoyanov, A. Ferrari, Y. Punie, K. Pannekeet and P. Sloep, "Experts' views on digital competence: Commonalities and differences," *Computers & Education*, pp. 473-481, 2013.
- [8] R. Graham, "The Global State of the Art in Engineering Education," Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA, USA, 2018.
- [9] D. Chr. Brooks and S. Grajek. "Students' Readiness to Adopt Fully Remote Learning," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://er.educause.edu/blogs/2020/3/students-readiness-to-adopt-fully-remote-learning>.
- [10] Why digital literacy matters. [Online]. Available: <https://natlib.govt.nz/schools/digital-literacy/understanding-digital-literacy/why-digital-literacy-matters>.
- [11] T. Heick. "9 Characteristics Of 21st Century Learning. Learning Models, The Future Of Learning," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.teachthought.com/learning-models/9-characteristics-of-21st-century-learning/?fbclid=IwAR0wRCcC1yWU4V9Y9nDWE4UYQuENuXL4UIVM0AiQ6k5OC9qFTYNkEHA9J6>.
- [12] L. Heitin "What Is Digital Literacy? - Digital Literacy: Forging Agreement on a Definition," Education Week, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.edweek.org/ew/articles/2016/11/09/what-is-digital-literacy.html>.
- [13] I. Yustyk "Analysis of services for the project activity under the blended learning setting, " Proceedings of the 47th SEFI Annual Conference 2019 "Industry 4.0 and Diversity in Engineering Education", pp. 1286-1296, 2019.

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